

**STATISTICAL STUDY OF EMPLOYMENT OF THE
POPULATION: AN INTEGRATED APPROACH**

Shavkat Muhammadiyevich Ortikov

Termiz State University Teacher

of “Economics and Management” Dept., Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: The article considers the existing methodological approaches to the study of employment. It is proved that the integrated approach to the study of the concept "employment" involving the study of employment not only from the perspective of its main economic characteristics, but also from the perspective of the internal structure of employment is of an important theoretical and practical value now. The author accentuated social, public and private, territorial and regional, sectoral, professional, and gender components as the main parts of the employment structure which are autonomous and independent on the one hand but don't exist in isolation from each other and participate in the process of labor and employment market as a whole on the other hand. Author's special attention was paid to the necessity to analyze the combination of factors under the influence of which the structure of employment is formed and modified and which were combined into several main groups depending on specification, these are demographic, economic, social, and operational factors.

Keywords: employment, unemployment, employment structure, employment factors, approaches to the study of employment.

The current stage of development of the Russian economy is accompanied by serious changes in the sphere of employment of the population, while the process of employment formation is mostly spontaneous territorial in nature and needs a special

incentive mechanism, since if the existing situation persists, the employment sphere will act as a serious constraint on the sustainable development of both individual regions and Uzbekistan as a whole [3].

In the modern social economy, employment is one of the main economic categories, the complexity and ambiguity of which cause numerous discussions. The problems of employment research occupy one of the leading places in the labor economy, since employment is not only the basis of the existence of society, but also a factor of economic growth and macroeconomic stability. Modern scientists have made a significant contribution to the development of theoretical, methodological and practical foundations for the formation of the mechanism and regulation of the labor market and employment: only in the nineties of the twentieth century, more than 250 works on employment issues were published in Russia and the CIS countries [2]. At the same time, it should be noted that a unified approach to the study of the labor market and employment has not yet been developed. During the period of industrial development, many scientists began to understand that employment is closely interrelated with unemployment, which is the reverse side of employment, and the employment problem must be solved as an employment problem. Modern views on the study of employment and unemployment problems are characterized by several areas of research, among which there are approaches based on the study of macroeconomic factors of increasing labor activity, which include the growth of the national economy, the monetary policy of the state, the globalization of the labor market, international migration. This approach is primarily followed by foreign economists, such as J. Gelbrait, J. Kornai, J. Schumpeter [1]. The approach to the analysis of employment from the perspective of microeconomic factors, such as the development and improvement of organizational and legal forms

of management, the expansion of the scope of labor application, state support for effectively operating enterprises and organizations, the creation and preservation of jobs, is characteristic of R. Kapelyushnikov, S. Kuzmin. [4]. At the same time, the methods of analysis and employment models based solely on the economic approach cannot always explain the essence of what is happening in the labor market, and the recommendations made on their basis are often erroneous.

Recently, there has been an increasing understanding of the importance of not only the economic component of people's life, but also other areas, principles and goals of human life. Thus, a meaningful study of the category "employment" involves its study not only from the standpoint of economic characteristics, but also from the standpoint of the internal structure of employment, when the term "structure" is understood as the relationship of many elements characterized by different forms and sizes. There are such links of the employment structure as social, public-private, territorial-regional, sectoral, professional-qualification and gender, which, on the one hand, are autonomous and have an independent meaning, but, on the other, do not exist separately from each other and participate in the process of forming the labor market and employment as a whole, the social structure of employment of the population characterizes changes in the structure of society associated with the reorientation of the class structure of society. During the period of socio-economic reforms, the structure of society both in Russia as a whole and in its individual regions has become more complicated due to the growing differentiation of income of the population and the deepening of interregional social inequality. The study of such changes is of fundamental importance for the correct understanding of the essence and nature of the social processes taking place in society, and making competent management decisions in order to regulate them. The

need to study changes in the social structure of employment is also due to the fact that the ongoing reforms are accompanied by a number of problems that are directly related to the decline in the standard of living of the population, which in turn is an indicator of their adverse impact on the labor market and socio-economic development, especially in certain regions of Uzbekistan.

The existing public-private employment structure in the Soviet era has been seriously transformed with the country's transition to a market economy: employment in the public sector has sharply decreased and employment in the private sector has grown rapidly, while growth has occurred mainly in commercial structures where hired labor is used. A prerequisite for the adequate functioning of the labor market and employment of the population is the productive interaction of business and government agencies. Although the forms and methods of this interaction vary significantly depending on the degree of development of market relations in specific regions, public authorities are still not free from fulfilling their social obligations related to public and national interests, and the business environment, in turn, is a source and driving force for the development and increase of public wealth.

The territorial and regional structure of employment characterizes significant indicators of economic development of regions: the level of development of territories rich in natural resources; the degree of use of labor potential in natural and economic conditions; economic activity of the population in the region; the number and proportion of the employed and unemployed population. Also, when studying the territorial and regional structure of employment, the analysis of internal and external migration takes a special place, since it has a serious impact on demographic processes that lead to changes in both the gender and age and social structure of

employment of the population in the regions from where migrants leave and where they come.

Each stage of the transformation of the economy is characterized by the dynamics of the sectoral structure of employment, which is an objective reflection of all the structural shifts taking place in the economy. It responds in a certain way to all changes in socio-economic development: it is accompanied by the wholesale displacement of certain types of economic activities that are going into the past from production and the mass involvement of workers in new professions and specialties in the economy. The study of the sectoral structure of employment of the population allows us to analyze the features of economic development of both a separate region and the country as a whole and draw conclusions about whether a particular economic system is in a state of crisis or whether it is characterized by stable economic growth, accompanied by an increase in the number of people employed in socially oriented and knowledge-intensive spheres of economic activity.

The professional and qualification structure of employment is a rather ambiguous concept that includes three, although quite closely related, but at the same time independent concepts: the professional structure of the employed, its qualification structure, as well as the content of the qualification itself. The professional structure is understood as a set of representatives of various professions and professional groups, the qualification structure is a set of employees of different qualification levels, the content of the qualification is a set of skills, experience, knowledge and other components that are mandatory for performing a specific job. The personnel potential of the population employed in the Russian economy has fairly high professional and qualification characteristics. A distinctive feature of the modern economic situation is the rapid scientific and technological development, in

connection with which the emphasis is shifted from material production to the realization and development of human abilities, which has now turned from the main factor of production into the most important driving force of economic development: a large share of labor productivity growth is provided by the human factor. This explains the increased attention to the analysis of social and labor relations, which affect the main interests of both the entire population and individual social groups.

The need to analyze the employment structure in this aspect is felt most acutely today due to the fact that against the general background of the excess supply existing in the labor market, there is also an unsatisfied demand for vacant jobs, the main reason for which is the discrepancy between the actual available qualifications to the requirements for employees of the profession, since the labor market and the market of educational services function separately from each other. The concept of the gender structure of employment was introduced into scientific circulation in order to assess the level of horizontal (by types of economic activity), vertical (in the official and professional-qualification context) segregation and to describe the unequal ratio of men and women employed in the economy. The existing problems of gender employment of the population are among the most urgent in various spheres of life of modern society: political, economic, social. The legislation in the field of politics and economics, formed in recent years in the Russian Federation, is aimed at creating a basis for the development of a gender-oriented and gender-balanced policy [5].

The structure of employment of the population changes under the influence of a large set of factors that differ both in their orientation and in the degree of impact.

Therefore, within the framework of statistical research of employment of the population, it becomes important to study not only the structure of employment as

such, but also the factors that directly affect the structure of employment of the population, which, depending on the specifics, can be combined into several main groups: demographic, economic, social, and industrial.

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